

ENGLISH CUSTOMS TERMS AND THEIR ORIGIN

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Annotation: *The purpose of the article is to provide a brief overview of English customs terms, their origin and historical background. The article defines some customs, which are popular around the world and gives definitions to these terms.*

Key words: *English customs, Christmas, Boxing day, Christmas carols, Valentine's day, Shrove Tuesday, Easter, May Day, Bonfire night, Cheese Rolling, Morris Dancing*

When we talk about English Customs, we can understand the customs of English speaking countries. As we know there are a lot of English speaking countries, and that is why I chose for this work one of them, which is important around the world with its history of origin and spreading of the language. It is the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland.

So, a good start to gaining some understanding of the lives of people living in a country is to look at their cherished customs and traditions. These illustrate not only what is important to the people living there, but also how they relax and have fun.

Britain is full of culture and traditions which have been around for hundreds of years. British customs and traditions are famous all over the world. When people think of Britain they often think of people drinking tea, eating fish and chips and wearing bowler hats, but there is more to Britain than just those things.

Some of the British culture, customs and traditions that vary from the weird to the wonderful, from the traditional to the popular, and from the simple to the grand.

There will be listed some customs terms, which are so popular around the world.

Christmas

Christmas, Christian festival celebrating the birth of Jesus. The English term Christmas ("mass on Christ's day") is of fairly recent origin.

Many people think Christmas is on December the 25th and that's all there is to Christmas. However, for many people around the world, in different countries and in different Christian traditions, Christmas lasts for a lot longer than that - and it's even celebrated at different times! December 25th (or the late afternoon/evening of December 24th) is the date when most people celebrate Christmas.

In the UK , families often celebrate Christmas together, so they can watch each other open their presents!

Most families have a Christmas Tree in their house for Christmas. The decorating of the tree is usually a family occasion, with everyone helping. Christmas Trees were first popularised the UK by Prince Albert, the husband of Queen Victoria. Prince Albert was German, and thought that it would be good to use one of his ways of celebrating Christmas in England.

Boxing Day

The term is of British origin, and the Oxford English Dictionary traces its earliest print attribution to 1833, four years before Charles Dickens referred to it in “The Pickwick Papers.” The exact roots of the holiday name are unknown, but there are two leading theories, both of which are connected to charity traditionally distributed to lower classes on the day after Christmas.

The name comes from a time when the rich used to box up gifts to give to the poor.

Boxing Day was traditionally a day off for servants, and the day when they received a special Christmas box from their masters. The servants would also go home on Boxing Day to give Christmas boxes to their families.

Boxing Day is the day after Christmas Day and falls on 26 December.

Christmas carols

A Christmas carol is a carol (a song or hymn) on the theme of Christmas, traditionally sung at Christmas itself or during the surrounding Christmas holiday season. The term noel has sometimes been used, especially for carols of French origin. Christmas carols may be regarded as a subset of the broader category of Christmas music.

Valentine's Day

Valentine's Day (Saint Valentine's Day) is an occasion celebrated on February 14. It is the traditional day on which people express their love for each other by sending Valentine's cards, presenting flowers, or offering confectionery. Valentine icon

There were many Christians names Valentine. According to the Catholic Encyclopaedia, at least three Saint Valentines are mentioned who are associated with 14 February. One is described as a priest at Rome,

another as a Bishop of Interamna (now Terni in Italy) and the other lived and died in Africa.

The Valentine that most experts believe is the actual one remembered on St. Valentine's Day was a Roman who was martyred for refusing to give up Christianity.

Each year in Britain, we spend around £503m on cards, flowers, chocolates and other gifts for Valentine's Day. Traditionally these were sent anonymously, but nowadays we often make it clear who is sending each 'Valentine'.

Shrove Tuesday(Pancake day)

The name Shrove comes from the old word "shrive" which means to confess. On Shrove Tuesday, in the Middle Ages, people used to confess their sins so that they were forgiven before the season of Lent began.

In the UK, Shrove Tuesday is also known as Pancake Day (or Pancake Tuesday to some people) because it is the one day of the year when almost everyone eats a pancake. Pancake Day (also known as Shrove Tuesday) is the last day before the period which Christians call Lent. It is traditional on this day to eat pancakes. Why are Pancakes eaten on Shrove Tuesday?

Lent is a time of abstinence, of giving things up. So Shrove Tuesday is the last chance to indulge yourself, and to use up the foods that aren't allowed in Lent. Pancakes are eaten on this day because they contain fat, butter and eggs which were forbidden during Lent.

Shrove Tuesday is celebrated the day before Ash Wednesday and is therefore the final day before the commencement of Lent, a Christian festival leading up to Easter Sunday (Easter Day).

Shrove Tuesday always falls 47 days before Easter Sunday, so the date varies from year to year and falls between 3 February and 9 March.

Easter

Easter is the time for holidays, festivals and a time for giving chocolate Easter eggs. But Easter means much more....

Easter is the oldest and the most important Christian Festival, the celebration of the death and coming to life again of Jesus Christ. For Christians, the dawn of Easter Sunday with its message of new life is the high point of the Christian year.

Easter is the story of Jesus' last days in Jerusalem before his death. The Easter story includes Maundy Thursday (the Last supper leading to the Eucharist), Good Friday (the day on which Jesus was crucified) and Easter Day (the day on which Jesus came back to life).

It is a sad story because Jesus was killed. But the story has a very happy ending, because Jesus came back to life and visited his friends and followers once more. He did not die at all, but went back up to Heaven to be with God, his father.

Pagan traditions give us the English word "Easter" which comes from the word "Eostre". The Anglo-Saxon word for April was "Eostre-monath" (the month of openings). However, it should be remembered that Christians celebrated the resurrection of Christ long before the word "Easter" was used, and the word they used for the celebration was "Pascha", which is derived from and linked to the Jewish festival of Passover.

At Easter time in the UK we have two bank holidays (public holidays): Good Friday and Easter Monday. This means that many families can enjoy a long weekend together.

May Day

The first day of the month of May is known as May Day. It is the time of year when warmer weather begins and flowers and trees start to blossom. It is said to be a time of love and romance. It is when people celebrate the coming of summer with lots of different customs that are expressions of joy and hope after a long winter.

Traditional English May Day celebrations include Morris dancing, crowning a May Queen and dancing around a Maypole. Although summer does not officially begin until June, May Day marks its beginning. May Day celebrations have been carried out in England for over 2000 years.

Bonfire Night

Bonfire night is a celebration in Britain commemorating the failure of the plan to assassinate King James I in 1605. This plan is known as the Gunpowder plot. One prominent member of the English Catholics who collaborated for the plan was Guy Fawkes. That is why Bonfire night is considered synonymous to Guy Fawkes Night. This event is celebrated on November 5. On this night, bonfires are lit and people gather to enjoy treats warmed by the fire. Fireworks also fill the night sky as different forms of entertainment keep the crowd occupied. An effigy of Guy Fawkes is burned and destroyed during the celebration.

Bonfire night is criticized for its social and environmental impact, as the celebration poses major security risks and pollution concerns.

Cheese Rolling

Cheese rolling is an unusual British tradition that involves a ball of Double Gloucester cheese and a crowd that is willing to chase it for fun.

It takes place on Cooper's Hill in Gloucestershire, England (Show on Map), with a slope so steep the participants have no choice but to stumble their way down to the finish line where, hopefully, the cheese awaits.

The cheese rolling event takes place every Spring Bank Holiday Monday of the year. Local participants and visitors from all over the world gather at 12 in the afternoon to participate in or witness this sport which dates back to the 15th century when people are assumed to do similar activities as harvest rituals, among other theories.

Morris Dancing

Morris dancing is both art and history in motion. It usually involves dancing with sticks, handkerchiefs or swords in a style that is depicted mainly by location. Some styles include Cotswold from the South Midlands and Longsword in Yorkshire. This type of dance is typically performed on specific occasions and seasons such as early summer for Oxfordshire and Christmas and New Year for Yorkshire. However, morris dancing can still be performed in other instances.

The provided customs terms show that they are not only popular in The UK, but we can find people who are doing or celebrating these customs all around the world. And learning such kind of information gives us a lot of pleasure.

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